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Challenges and Future Directions

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Consolidation of Professional Competences in the Cultural Sector. A Case Study of Experiences in Monitoring and Evaluation Training

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Abstract

“Musei di Tutti” (Museums for All) is a network of museums in Florence and Fiesole that promotes a transformative vision of cultural institutions as spaces for relationship and co-creation. Their approach to heritage interpretation shifts the focus from objects to people, aiming to activate learning, inclusion, and well-being through participatory and conscious engagement with culture, especially for underrepresented audiences. The project “Ve li raccontiamo noi! I musei visti dai più piccoli” (“We tell you about them! Museums seen by the youngest”) involved children as co-authors of museum narratives, enhancing their creativity, communication, teamwork, and sense of connection to the museum. Within this framework, the University of Florence conducted an action-research initiative to validate the network’s innovative models, positioning museums as catalysts for social change and well-being, and to reflect on the transversal competences of museum educators, crucial for community activation and participatory interpretation of cultural heritage.

Introduction

Cultural institutions today are called upon to take on a multifunctional and socially relevant role that goes beyond the preservation and conservation of cultural heritage (Ashworth, 2011) and become catalysts for well-being, social cohesion and lifelong learning (Falk, 2022; Del Gobbo et al., 2018; Pop and Borza, 2015). They need to adapt to new challenges, such as actively engaging the public and local communities, ensuring accessibility and inclusion, and developing consistent skills among their workforces. Continuous monitoring and formative evaluation of cultural practices is crucial in such processes.

The article describes some of the results of a participative action-research process promoted by the thematic museum network “Musei di Tutti”¹ (Museums for All) in collaboration with the University of Florence. Over the years, this network, made up of six museums² in the municipalities of Fiesole and Florence (Italy), has become increasingly aware that museums should shift their focus “from things to people” and make the public’s enjoyment of cultural heritage the main object of their attention and educational activities. The project “Ve li raccontiamo noi! I musei visti dai più piccoli”¹ (We tell you about them! The museums seen by the youngest), launched in 2023 with a first edition for children aged 6 to 10, aims to actively involve this young audience and, consequently, their families, making them protagonists in the planning and realisation of museum visits for their peers. The aim is to develop a personal story about cultural heritage from children to other children and to make them promoters and producers of cultural services¹ and new narratives about cultural heritage.

The following chapters briefly describe the action-research carried out in the framework of this project by the research team of the Department of Educational Sciences of the University of Florence. Experience has shown the importance of consolidating the transversal skills of museum educators for the success of initiatives aimed at community activation and participatory interpretation of cultural heritage (Marconi, 2024).

Conceptual Framework

The approach of the “Musei di Tutti” (Museums for All) network and in particular the project “Ve li raccontiamo noi!” (We tell you about them!), which emerged from the participatory action-research developed by the Department of Education at the University of Florence, fits seamlessly into the current debate on the transformative role of museums in society.

Cultural fruition is still often perceived as an elitist activity reserved for people with a certain background. However, the contemporary debate on the new paradigms of cultural heritage and the holistic function of culture contradicts this view and argues that culture and cultural spaces belong to everyone, as they interweave multiple meanings and levels of interpretation that are accessible to all. The role of the museum today would be to facilitate contact and encounters with the dense universe of meanings contained in cultural artefacts and to strengthen its social function as a “living space” and place of cultural encounter and participation.

The paradigm shift described above in relation to the role of museums in society, finds a solid reference in the process that led to the reformulation of the definition of the term

museum by the international organisation ICOM in 2022. In the new description, the museum is recognised as playing a key role in lifelong learning, inclusion and accessibility in the service of society and communities. These assumptions are reflected in important international conventions in the cultural debate, such as the Faro Convention (2005) and the Convention on Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003), which propose putting people at the centre of cultural processes and activities and emphasising the right to cultural participation and the transmission of heritage, including in innovative ways.

Furthermore, in the new ICOM definition of the term “museum”, the word “sustainability” appears in a particularly significant way, as it is clearly in continuity with the goals of the UN 2030 Agenda, which assigns cultural heritage an active and fundamental role in the areas of education, gender equality, sustainable development, inclusive territorial transformation and intercultural dialogue (ICOMOS, 2021). Moreover, such a new term in the museum definition probably refers to a growing body of literature that recognises the role of culture as a “fourth pillar” of sustainability and sustainable development alongside the three traditional pillars (economic, social and environmental) (Throsby, 2008; Hawkes, 2001), but also as a moderating element of the different areas of sustainability and as a prerequisite for the concept of sustainability itself (Soini and Dessein, 2016; Soini and Birkeland, 2014).

In light of these considerations, it must be emphasised that there is an urgent need to rethink the role, activities and training of cultural professionals working in museums and cultural institutions, focusing on transversal skills that can more strongly emphasise the participatory and co-creative aspects of cultural work. For example, the ability to be guided by the paradigms of sustainability enables museum educators to work with a long-term vision and to integrate cultural activities into broad development strategies of both organisations and territories. Knowledge of programmes and principles promoted by international organisations helps to act according to common standards. At the same time, emotional awareness and the ability to activate value dialogues promote a positive working environment and more effective heritage education techniques. Finally, flexibility and adaptability enable effective work in interdisciplinary programmes that increase the impact on different areas and aspects of cultural activities in the territories.

Developing and raising awareness of transversal competences among museum educators is of strategic importance for the effectiveness of actions to promote the activation and well-being of communities through culture. Likewise, the evaluation of projects and processes developed from this perspective is crucial to understand whether they are truly transformative.

Methodology

The participatory action-research that accompanied the project “Ve li raccontiamo noi!” (We tell you about them!), followed a collaborative and methodologically pluralistic approach (Multi and Mixed Methods, MMR) (DeJonckheere et al., 2019; Creswell and Clark, 2011; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The team, composed of researchers from the University of Florence, museum managers and educators, developed a research plan to collect evidence on the effectiveness of the educational practices implemented.

The university research unit set two main objectives: to develop common evaluation tools for the project experience, differentiated by target groups (museum educators, children, parents); to identify the elements of project effectiveness and the specificities of the network’s functioning³. Two research strategies were chosen, which were carried out in parallel⁴:

1. Participant observation: Creation of three observation sheets to analyse the actions of museum educators, children and parents during the first phase of the project in each museum. The observation sheets were designed taking into account both the objectives of the museum network and the objectives of the university research unit.
2. Administration of questionnaires: design and administration² of three separate questionnaires specifically developed for the project and aimed at museum educators, children and parents⁵. The questionnaires were developed through triangulation of data from: participant observation, academic literature and collaborative definition of research evaluation objectives.

The entire process of interpreting the collected data was conducted from an integrated perspective combining the hermeneutic and outcome-oriented paradigm within the team.

Results

The process enabled museum managers and educators to adopt methods and tools to move from an informal assessment of the results of their activities to a data-driven evaluation that demonstrates the degree to which the defined objectives have been achieved. The process, using a “backward” approach, also allowed for a better clarification of the objectives and dimensions of the educational project. This clarification and the resulting awareness formed the basis for critical-reflective processes to analyse, consolidate, improve, and, above all, learn from the experience.

The collaborative experience of participatory action-research led to some recommendations for the future, which the team also considers useful for other museum coordinators or

coordinators of cultural services, museum educators and policy makers. Below is a summary of the key recommendations.

Recommendations for Museum Coordinators or Coordinators of Cultural Services

Supporting education and participation projects through culture requires a strategic and integrated vision that recognises the value of these activities both as a cultural service to the public and as a concrete professional development opportunity for the staff involved. The project objectives should be in line with the cultural policy of the institution and the territory and promote or activate stable and significant collaborations with other territorial realities.

For the project to work well, effective internal and external communication must be guaranteed and favourable conditions must be created for the exchange of knowledge and joint reflection on practises. It is equally important to work with a view to the continuity of the project and to build trusting relationships with the public.

To ensure consistency and quality, it is essential to share the conception, planning and organisation of activities with all stakeholders involved in order to develop a common and shared vision of the project's meaning and objectives. Finally, the promotion of participatory monitoring and evaluation enables the identification of strengths, the detection of points of criticism and the identification of opportunities for improvement with a view to collective learning and the continuous growth of the entire museum organisation.

Recommendations for Museum Educators

The starting point for museum educators is to recognise the central role of the audience. They should maintain an open and receptive attitude to what arouses the curiosity and wonder of the viewership. They should demonstrate the ability to adapt content and methods in response to the stimuli that emerge during the experience and work with participants to define the meaning and direction of the activities.

When planning and running the meetings, it is important to pay attention to the composition of the groups to ensure a meaningful and accessible experience for each participant. During the experience, a balance should also be struck between the educational objectives of the project and the specific needs of the participants.

The environment should be calm to encourage listening and create a welcoming climate that stimulates imagination and a sense of wonder, fundamental elements for engaging and effective learning.

It is advisable to introduce and conclude each activity with a short discussion with the participants; this provides a valuable opportunity to gather feedback and deepen viewpoints.

The evaluation moments can be designed or led by the participants themselves to reinforce their role as protagonists, or they can be worked out with their coordinators or managers.

Finally, it is useful for museum educators to critically reflect on their work and compare themselves with their colleagues and their coordinators or managers in order to improve not only the quality of the proposed activities, but also their pedagogical, relational and planning skills.

Recommendations for Policy Makers

It is crucial that policy makers recognise the strategic role of museums as active and overarching actors within cultural, social, health and educational policies. Museums are not only places where cultural heritage is preserved, but they can effectively contribute to the implementation of integrated public policies that can have a concrete and positive impact on the territory and the people who inhabit it. At the same time, museums can be valorised as important actors within the territorial welfare system, as they are able to respond to needs, activate resources and create paths of integration, well-being and active citizenship.

Conclusions

The project “Ve li raccontiamo noi!” (We tell you about them!) shows the transformative potential of museums when they open up to democratisation processes and put people “at the centre”. The participatory action-research has shown how collaboration between cultural institutions, universities and communities can trigger positive processes of organisational growth, relationship and territorial network building, learning, well-being, skills and professionalism development. In particular, the collaborative approach has made it possible to understand how the transversal competences of cultural practitioners are crucial to respond to the needs of territories and communities for well-being and sustainability.

The collaboratively formulated recommendations presented in this paper provide a practical guide and considerations to promote the active enjoyment of cultural heritage and ensure that museums are valued and recognised as places of debate, dialogue, well-being and sense-making. Ultimately, the work confirms the importance of continuing with new editions of the project and deepening the reflection on evaluation tools and competences needed for the future of the cultural sector.

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Endnotes

1. <https://www.firenzefiesolemusei.net/>
2. The following museums are part of the thematic museum network “Museums for All”: Palazzo Vecchio, Stefano Bardini, Innocenti, Bandini, Civic Archaeological, Arena Archaeological and Primo Conti. The network is coordinated by Maria Chiara Berni, Silvia Borsotti, Chiara Ferrari, Arabella Natalini and Valentina Zucchi.
3. <https://www.firenzefiesolemusei.net/2023/10/14/ve-li-racontiamo-noi-i-musei-visti-dai-piu-piccoli-iscriviti/>
4. The latter will be discussed in more detail in the results section. The overall results of the participatory action-research are described in the volume: Del Gobbo, G., Marconi, S., Borsotti, S. and Zucchi, V. (2024) *Museums Seen by Children. Experiences of Heritage Interpretation and Community Activation of the “Musei Di Tutti” (Museums for All) Network*. Lecce: Pensa Multimedia.
5. The action-research phase took place between September 2023 and May 2024. The “Museums for All” network project was designed in two parts: 1. cycle of co-design sessions and training of children as museum guides for their peers, between October and December 2023; 2. cycle of guided tours by children involved in the project for their peers, between December 2023 and April 2024.
6. Anonymous and in paper form to facilitate completion and ensure accessibility.
7. A total of 67 responses were collected: 32 from the children, 27 from their parents, and 8 from the museum educators involved in the project.

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